

Financial Integrity: An In-Depth Exploration of Internal Control and Audit Triumphs in Fostering Resilient Business Strategies

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ABSTRACT: In the intricate dance between internal control and audit success, this study unveils a harmonious relationship through a comprehensive case study at Alpha. The empirical findings resonate with theoretical constructs, spotlighting deficiencies in customer receivables and asset procurement. This is not just a diagnosis; it is a revelation of opportunities for immediate correction and a blueprint for ongoing operational excellence. The practical assessment serves as a poignant exemplar, showcasing how a nuanced understanding and implementation of internal controls not only safeguard financial integrity but also elevates audit missions to comprehensive and insightful evaluations. The study underscores the critical role of auditors in fortifying internal controls, ensuring a meticulous examination of Alpha's financial landscape. As we revisit the central question of the study—how internal control contributes to the success of accounting and financial audits—the case study unequivocally asserts that internal control is more than a formality. It emerges as a fundamental element ensuring the reliability of financial information, fostering transparency, adherence to standards, and guaranteeing the triumph of audit missions. The substantial deficiencies unearthed in customer receivables management and asset acquisition processes at Alpha underscore the urgent need for enhancements in internal control. Recommendations stemming from these observations offer concrete paths to strengthen financial operations, providing practical perspectives to enhance the quality of audit missions in a complex financial environment. While acknowledging study limitations tied to its specificity, the insights gleaned provide a valuable contribution to understanding the practical importance of internal control. This study paves the way for future research in this indispensable domain of corporate finance, emphasizing the significance of financial resonance for sustained audit triumphs at Alpha and beyond.

KEYWORDS: internal control, audit success, financial integrity, customer receivables, asset acquisition, comprehensive analysis, financial operations, corporate finance, transparency, audit missions, operational excellence

Introduction

In a world where financial transparency and corporate responsibility play an increasingly prominent role due to their impact on numerous economic and political decisions, it is crucial to meticulously plan a financial audit mission to ensure the effectiveness of the audit and the quality of the results. Previously, leaders of small businesses directly oversaw task execution and the speed of communication among staff, however, the need to finance their growth required seeking external capital. These funds were granted by individuals who were not necessarily informed about the risks involved. Furthermore, the proliferation of financial scandals in recent years has led to an increase in charges against executives. Thus, false financial statements, certified by auditors, and behaviors contrary to the interests of the company have been exposed. Boards of directors, in turn, have been accused of wielding their power based more on personal interest than that of the company (Pallusseau 1996). All these factors give rise to a notable reconsideration of the current corporate governance process, questioning its ability to act consistently and effectively manage conflicts and the interests of

all stakeholders. Thus arises the notion of scrutinizing the relevance of internal control in the context of planning a financial audit mission, with the goal of minimizing risks and enhancing corporate governance. A significant added value for the company, the statutory audit mission also serves as a revealer of risks and dysfunctions within an organization. It represents a genuine public interest mission aimed at ensuring the credibility of financial information. Indeed, over the past decade, audit firms have evolved into pivotal players in the economic realm, irrespective of the political orientation of the country and the legal structure allowed for businesses, trade, and financial establishments.

Internal control and audit are complementary elements that work together to restore confidence in the processes, activities, and transactions conducted by organizations, both internally and with external parties. Audit, being an external examination of the quality of collected, processed, and transmitted information, serves as an assurance (usually external) of the proper functioning and adequacy of internal control procedures and the compliance of the product or service with applicable standards. Internal control encompasses all procedures and mechanisms deployed by each company to ensure the relevance of the process related to the collection, processing, and transmission of information. It must ensure that all transactions are understandable, correctly assessed, and controlled in accordance with applicable standards (whether internal to the organization, specific to a sector, or international).

The analysis of internal control can play a key role in audit planning by helping auditors understand the risks of error or fraud in the processes of the audited entity, as well as the most critical areas of the business, and plan appropriate audit procedures. Additionally, this method also assists auditors in identifying weaknesses in the company's internal control systems, allowing them to plan the most appropriate audit procedures to determine the accuracy and reliability of transactions and financial information.

Despite the importance of internal control analysis in guiding the planning of external audits, several challenges can complicate this process. Auditors may face difficulties in understanding companies' internal systems and key processes, potentially compromising the reliability of internal control analysis. Additionally, determining the areas most at risk for the company and those requiring particular attention during external audits can be challenging. This raises the question of how to optimize the use of internal control analysis to effectively guide the planning of external audits.

In the subsequent sections of this article, the focus is placed on the practical application of the theoretical insights derived from an in-depth case study conducted in the context of an auditing internship. This empirical study aimed to bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and real-world audit practices. By engaging in comprehensive interviews with experienced auditors, practical perspectives on the challenges and nuances encountered in the field were sought. Moving beyond the theoretical framework, the results section presents the findings of the case study, providing a detailed analysis of the observed practices within the audited organization. These findings are crucial in contextualizing the relevance of internal controls in the audit process and assessing their impact on the overall effectiveness of financial and accounting audits. The discussion section confronts the results with the theoretical underpinnings established in the literature review. This critical analysis aims to decipher the practical implications of the identified patterns and discrepancies, providing a nuanced understanding of how internal control intricacies can influence the success of an audit mission.

The concluding section synthesizes the contributions made by this study to the field of auditing. It reaffirms the importance of a robust internal control system in guiding and enhancing audit processes. Additionally, the limitations and prospects of this study are discussed, opening avenues for future research and development in the realm of auditing practices.

Auditor and the Agency Theory Perspective

In recent years, scandals affecting the American economy (Enron, Vivendi), as well as the global economy, have triggered a paradoxical reassessment of the role of the statutory auditor, or the legal auditor of a company's accounts. The statutory auditor's mission is to certify the sincerity, regularity, and faithful representation of financial statements published by the concerned entities. Additionally, their role involves safeguarding investors in financial markets and ensuring the smooth functioning of the economy. According to numerous theories, this function is crucial for reducing information gaps among economic actors by confirming the accuracy of financial data, forming the basis for economic and financial decisions such as investment and financing. However, the widely accepted definition of agency theory emerged in 1976, introduced by Jensen and Meckling. According to their seminal work, "Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure" (Jensen and Meckling 1976), an agency relationship is defined as 'a contract in which at least one party (the principal) engages another party (the agent) to perform a task on their behalf, involving the delegation of a certain decision-making authority to the agent.'

Shareholders aim to maximize company profits, and according to theory, executives should act in the shareholders' best interests to enhance the company's value. However, executives often prioritize their own utility function and personal interests, particularly in the context of job retention. While the general expectation is that management should work for the benefit of shareholders by maximizing value and profits, executives may lean towards maintaining their status while optimizing their personal utility and self-interest.

The agency theory asserts that auditing is a crucial tool for signaling, regulating management, and resolving conflicts of interest. Effective audits, accompanied by comprehensive reports, are vital to minimizing information asymmetry between management and stakeholders. In Morocco, auditing is governed by Law 17-95 for anonymous companies, requiring the appointment of auditors to examine annual financial accounts. Law No. 5-96 extends this mandate to other commercial companies with a turnover exceeding 50 million dirhams. The Chartered Accountants of Morocco (OEC) sets professional standards emphasizing ethical principles, independence, professional diligence, and confidentiality (IFAC 2010). Aligned with agency theory, these standards ensure auditors fulfill their responsibilities independently and competently, preserving the interests of shareholders and stakeholders. Simultaneously, these regulations fortify the accuracy and reliability of financial data, fostering trust among shareholders and stakeholders.

The Rigorous Framework of Auditing: Financial Integrity and Stakeholder Trust

In the realm of professional auditing, a meticulous and comprehensive approach is imperative to ensure the reliability of financial information. The auditor's due diligence encompasses a rigorous examination of accounting documents, guaranteeing adherence to standards and legal obligations. This involves not only scrutinizing the meticulousness of accounting records but also conducting thorough asset and liability inventories. Additionally, the evaluation of internal controls becomes a focal point, demanding an in-depth assessment of organizational processes and their effectiveness. The auditor meticulously examines the design and implementation of control systems, conducts tests, and engages in interviews to affirm the efficacy of these internal safeguards. Substantive tests further scrutinize various financial elements, employing methodologies like consistency and validity tests to verify accuracy and reliability. The culmination of these efforts results in comprehensive reports—general, special, and management—that communicate findings, opinions, and recommendations to stakeholders. Despite the rigorous process, auditors bear significant responsibilities, including civil liability for compensating

third parties, potential criminal liability for violations of laws, and disciplinary liability governed by professional bodies. This multifaceted role underscores the critical role auditors play in upholding financial integrity and fostering trust in the business landscape.

Risk-Based Audit Approach

The risk-based approach in auditing is crucial for targeted and efficient audit practices. It allows auditors to focus on areas with significant risks, ensuring a tailored and effective audit. This approach emphasizes the identification and evaluation of potential risks, enabling auditors to customize procedures and controls to address specific challenges. By concentrating efforts on critical areas, auditors enhance the relevance and efficiency of their work, contributing to the quality and reliability of financial information.

Risk mapping plays a key role in recognizing and analyzing risks during the audit. It helps identify critical areas that need special attention and those that can undergo streamlined verifications. Auditors consider various risks, including inherent risks related to the nature of the entity's activities, control risks in detecting anomalies, and detection risks where auditors may overlook significant anomalies. Considering these risks is crucial during financial audit missions, influencing the nature and extent of audit work. Identifying and understanding these risks allows auditors to adopt a tailored and targeted approach, reducing the risk of significant anomalies in financial statements.

Internal Control Assessment as an Intermediate Phase in the CAC Mission

Necessity of Internal Control Appreciation:

Internal control, evolving alongside business activities, now encompasses strategic aspects beyond mere financial dimensions. The evaluation phase aims to assess the quality and effectiveness of the mechanisms and procedures implemented by the company to ensure transparent and sound management of its activities. Specific objectives include safeguarding assets, ensuring compliance with laws and regulations, aligning with strategic directions, and ensuring reliability and integrity of financial information. The globally recognized COSO (Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission) framework provides a comprehensive reference for understanding and implementing internal control.

The COSO Framework:

The COSO framework, a recognized international standard, serves as a vital conceptual guide for internal control systems. It introduces innovative principles and provides a structured approach for organizations to develop tailored internal control systems. According to COSO, internal control is a process formulated by an organization's board, executives, and employees to ensure the achievement of three objectives: operational performance and optimization, reliability of financial and management information, and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. The framework delineates three categories of objectives—operations, reporting, and compliance—enabling organizations to address various facets of internal control. Additionally, COSO comprises five components, covering the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring. Each component plays a crucial role in establishing an effective internal control system, emphasizing the importance of consistency and coordination in its implementation across all levels of the organization (Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission 2013).

Methodology of Internal Control Evaluation Adopted by Auditors

Understanding Procedures:

Detailed examination of procedures is essential for a comprehensive evaluation. This includes understanding guidelines for task execution, document usage and content, authorizations, and information processing. Various methods like interviews, descriptive questionnaires, and flowcharts are employed to grasp the intricacies of these procedures.

Interim Phase:

The interim phase, often conducted throughout the year, focuses on internal control assessment. Analytical review of previous period accounts, physical inventory, and other tasks are carried out during this phase. Depending on the assessment, the final scope of control tests may be adjusted.

Preliminary Evaluation of Internal Control:

This step involves identifying internal control cycles and audit objectives within each cycle, such as purchases from suppliers, sales to customers, treasury, equity, and payroll. Transactions within each cycle are scrutinized, and procedures must adhere to principles like initiation by authorized personnel and validation by responsible individuals.

Internal Control Letter:

A summary prepared at the end of the interim phase, the internal control letter highlights serious defects in the design or management of internal risks and suggests improvements for more efficient and economical methods. The letter serves as a crucial communication tool between the auditor and the company's management, focusing on enhancing internal controls to streamline the audit process.

Methodology

In the context of our statutory audit mission, we conducted a comprehensive study focused on the evaluation of internal control within a company in the animal feed sector. Our methodology was structured around three distinct phases.

The first phase involved semi-structured interviews with professionals in the field, and their analysis. This allowed us to gain insights into how internal control influences the understanding of the audited entity's processes and shapes the planning of the statutory audit mission.

The second phase focused on a thorough analysis of the mission's context. We carefully examined the company's financial statements, internal policies, and procedures. Taking into consideration the specificities of the animal feed sector, the associated major risks, and the internal controls in place to mitigate them, we aimed to obtain an overview of the environment in which the entity operates and identify key areas requiring a detailed assessment of internal controls.

Finally, the third step involved a meticulous assessment of internal control. We applied a structured approach by identifying essential controls and conducting tests. The goal was to evaluate the effectiveness of existing internal controls and formulate appropriate recommendations to strengthen these controls and enhance the overall quality of the audit mission. This study was approached from the angle of qualitative research. We opted for interviews with auditors due to their knowledge and experience in audit and internal control. We rigorously prepared for these interviews. Firstly, we compiled a list of auditors with extensive experience. Subsequently, we reached out to them through various means, including emails, messages on LinkedIn, and phone calls.

Case Company: Alpha

A case study approach has been chosen to delve deeply into the intricacies of the subject matter, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of specific instances.

Brief history:

The company Alpha, established in 2001 as a Limited Liability Company (SARL) with a registered capital of 6800 KMAD, operates in the animal feed sector, specializing in the production and marketing of poultry and livestock feed for over 20 years. Headquartered in Berrechid, Morocco, the company has experienced consistent growth over the years, expanding its product range and strengthening its position in the local market.

For the fiscal year 2022, Alpha reported a turnover of 856,694 KMAD. The company employs 47 personnel and operates under the normal tax regime.

Risk Areas in Operational Cycles:

In the evaluation of Alpha's internal controls, particularly within the sales and collection cycle and the fixed assets cycle, we identified various strengths and weaknesses. Our investigation, consisting of a comprehensive questionnaire and observations, illuminated crucial aspects within each cycle.

Primarily, it came to our attention that Alpha lacks both an operational procedures manual and an accounting procedures manual. Consequently, the explicit documentation of procedures for the company's accounting and operational transactions is absent, potentially leading to misunderstandings and procedural inconsistencies.

Furthermore, our analysis revealed a lax implementation of budgetary monitoring and controls within Alpha. Effective budgetary tracking and controls are indispensable to ensure alignment between the company's expenses and the budget, identification of variances, and the implementation of corrective measures if necessary. The absence of these management systems may result in budget overruns and a deficiency in financial control.

A notable lapse observed is Alpha's neglect of the principle of task segregation. Failure to segregate responsibilities concerning the initiation, authorization, and documentation of transactions may elevate the risk of errors and professional misconduct. It is crucial to emphasize that the points identified above are not exhaustive. These preliminary observations will serve as the foundation for a more detailed examination of risks associated with each specific section, including the sales and collection cycle and the fixed assets cycle.

Inventory Cycle:

The company does not have analytical accounting covering all its activities.

Cash Cycle:

Periodic physical inventory of cash is not conducted and is not formalized by a report.

Lack of a physical inventory of securities such as checks and promissory notes.

Fixed Assets Cycle:

- Alpha lacks criteria for choosing suppliers.
- Alpha does not establish a commissioning report for fixed assets.
- No physical inventory of fixed assets is conducted.

The Purchasing Cycle:

- The company lacks a budgetary control system to monitor and block purchase orders.
- The purchasing department does not engage in multiple supplier consultations.

The sales and collection cycle

- The company does not request customer balance sheets before granting credit sales.
- Alpha does not require guarantees such as bonds or endorsements from customers.
- Credit limits are not standardized for all customers.
- No credit recovery policy is in place.

Internal Control Evaluation:

In this section, a battery of tests has been undertaken to assess the effectiveness and reliability of internal procedures and controls implemented within Alpha Company. The objective of these

assessments is to ensure the relevance and reliability of the financial information produced by the company, as well as the prevention and detection of irregularities.

Accounts Receivable Reconciliation Test:

Within the scope of accounts receivable, we conducted a reconciliation test. Its purpose was to ensure that customer receivables were duly settled and cleared within reasonable time frames. The results enable us to identify risks associated with customer receivables recovery and recommend corrective measures or enhancements to internal controls if necessary.

Methodology:

The analysis involved examining the balances of customer accounts based on their age, categorized into time intervals of 0-89 days, 90-179 days, and so forth. Receivables exceeding 6 months were flagged as problematic.

Results:

Receivables aged over 6 months raise concerns, indicating potential issues in credit management. Notably, some clients have outstanding balances for more than a year, requiring attention.

Selling to a customer with a 6-month outstanding balance suggests inadequate credit monitoring.

We observed the presence of certain aged receivables dating back more than one year.

An alarming 22,224.33 KMAD constitutes receivables aged over 1 year, raising concerns about potential unmanageable debt.

Risk Implications:

Financial Overstatement: Unsettled receivables pose a risk of overestimating revenue if not provisioned for.

Impact on Auditor's Opinion: Failure to address such risks may impact the auditor's opinion, leading to a distorted financial picture.

Revenue Overstatement: A lack of provisions for aged receivables may overstate the company's revenue.

Misleading Financial Position: Overestimation of financial stability can mislead stakeholders like investors and creditors.

Analysis:

The results indicate a potential concern in the accounts receivable process, specifically related to the aging of certain receivables. This could suggest challenges in timely settlement and reconciliation, raising the risk of bad debts or liquidity issues. The recommendation for corrective measures or improvements in internal controls implies a proactive approach to address identified weaknesses and enhance the overall effectiveness of the financial control framework.

Conclusion:

The analysis reveals critical deficiencies in the credit management process, emphasizing the need for immediate corrective actions. Addressing these issues is crucial to present accurate financial information, ensuring transparency and maintaining the confidence of stakeholders.

The Routing Test:

Subsequently, we executed aimed at tracing the transactional journey from its initiation to its entry into the company's financial accounts. The objective was to ensure that each step of the process was respected.

Methodology:

Two representative clients, ABC and YYT, were randomly selected for this purpose. For Client ABC, all necessary procedures were followed, including providing a quotation, confirming the order, and receiving the advance. However, for Client YYT, a gap in the process was identified.

Results:

The analysis of the table reveals a lack of follow-up on the collection of customer receivables and a practice of delivering orders without a requirement for prior payment.

Risk Implications:

The routing test, designed to trace transactions from origin to accounting records, focused on two clients, ABC and YYT. While Client ABC showcased meticulous adherence to procedures, Client YYT exposed a critical lapse. Non-payment of the advance jeopardizes cash flow, essential for covering order-related costs. Furthermore, non-settlement of the invoice introduces risks of payment delays, cash flow challenges, and potential credibility issues for the company.

Analysis:

The deficiency unveiled in customer receivables monitoring and the identified risks underscore the importance of rectifying procedural gaps. Timely addressing these issues is imperative, not only for mitigating financial risks but also for sustaining the company's credibility in its business operations.

Conclusion:

The results indicate a deficiency in the monitoring of customer receivable collections and highlight potential risks associated with incomplete adherence to payment procedures, accentuating the urgency of corrective measures. Addressing these issues is crucial for maintaining financial stability and credibility in the business operation.

Compliance test

The compliance test within the fixed assets cycle aims to assess the compliance of internal procedures and legal requirements at Alpha. This examination identifies potential anomalies or non-conformities in the processes and recommends appropriate measures for rectification.

Methodology:

The acquisitions of assets were sampled, and the following assertions were ensured:

- Invoice duly issued
- Delivery note
- Purchase order
- Contradictory quotation
- Validation
- Investment request
- Stamped and recorded
- Consistency of order and delivery dates
- Installation certificate

Results:

- The company does not compare different quotations.
- The company does not formalize investment requests.
- Alpha does not formalize installation certificates for assets.

Risk Implications:

The company's failure to compare different quotations poses a risk to effective cost control. Without a proper comparison, the company may miss potential cost-saving opportunities, leading to inefficiencies in decision-making.

The absence of formalized installation certificates introduces operational inefficiencies that directly affect asset utilization. The deficiency in proper documentation poses a significant operational risk, potentially hindering Alpha's ability to derive maximum value from its investments. This inefficiency not only jeopardizes operational effectiveness but also raises concerns about the accuracy of operational data.

Analysis:

The findings from the compliance test indicate significant gaps in Alpha's asset acquisition procedures. These gaps pose risks in terms of cost management, financial oversight, operational efficiency, and compliance with regulatory requirements. The lack of comparison of quotations may result in suboptimal decision-making, while the absence of formalized investment requests can hinder financial planning and evaluation.

The non-formalization of installation certificates not only jeopardizes effective asset management but also introduces operational and compliance risks.

Conclusion:

The non-compliance issues identified in the conformity test emphasize the need for Alpha to enhance its procedures. Rectifying these issues is crucial for ensuring transparency, accountability, and compliance in the asset acquisition process.

Discussion

The empirical findings obtained from the practical assessment remarkably converge with the theoretical constructs expounded in the earlier literature review. The meticulous examination of internal controls has brought to the fore certain inadequacies, notably in the oversight of customer receivables and the procurement of assets. These discerned deficiencies seamlessly correlate with the theoretical emphasis on the pivotal role of robust internal controls in mitigating financial risks, as extensively discussed in the existing body of literature. The thorough examination of diverse cycles, including sales, procurement, and asset management, underscores the pervasive influence of internal controls in guiding audit procedures.

In synthesis, our on-the-ground evaluation substantiates the applicability and pertinence of the theoretical frameworks within the unique operational context of Alpha. The theoretical recommendations not only serve as a diagnostic tool for immediate corrective actions but also proffer a robust foundation for shaping the ongoing operational paradigms of the company.

This resonates, underscoring the symbiotic relationship between a sound internal control environment and the effectiveness of audit processes. This practical case serves as a poignant exemplification of how a nuanced understanding and implementation of internal controls are instrumental not only in ensuring financial integrity but also in steering audit missions towards comprehensive and insightful evaluations.

It underscores the critical need for auditors to consider, assess, and fortify internal controls as an integral component of their audit strategies, ensuring a comprehensive and meticulous examination of the audited entity's financial landscape.

Conclusion

In revisiting our central question of how a thorough analysis of internal control can be a key factor in the success of an accounting and financial audit, the case study conducted at Alpha unequivocally underscores that internal control is more than a mere formality. It emerges as a fundamental element ensuring the reliability of financial information. This places internal control at the forefront, fostering transparency, adherence to standards, and guaranteeing the triumph of audit missions.

Our comprehensive analysis of Alpha's internal control has brought forth substantial deficiencies in the management of customer receivables, the asset acquisition processes, and other critical financial operations. These revelations emphasize the urgent need for substantial enhancements in internal

control at Alpha to fortify the reliability of audited financial data. The results provide profound insights into how robust internal control can significantly augment the efficacy of audit missions.

Major contributions of our study lie in highlighting opportunities for improving internal control at Alpha. The recommendations stemming from our observations offer concrete paths to strengthen customer receivables management, optimize asset acquisition processes, and consequently enhance the reliability of financial information. These contributions provide practical perspectives to enhance the quality of audit missions in a complex and ever-evolving financial environment. However, it is crucial to acknowledge certain limitations in our study. The observations were based on a specific case, and while the recommendations are relevant for Alpha, they may require adjustments for application in different contexts. Additionally, our analysis focuses on operational and financial aspects, leaving out other potential dimensions of internal control. In summary, this study underscores the significance of internal control in the realm of audit success. Insights gleaned from our case study provide a valuable contribution to understanding the practical importance of internal control, paving the way for future comprehensive research in this indispensable domain of corporate finance.

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